

AUDIO-VISUAL PRESENTATION IN TEACHING MATHEMATICS: EFFECT ON LEARNERS' NUMERICAL ABILITY

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Audio-Visual Presentation in Teaching Mathematics: Effect on learners' Numerical Ability

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Abstract

This study was directed towards determining the effect of the audio-visual presentations on learners' numerical ability in teaching Mathematics at Gani L. Abpi College, Incorporated - Madia Campus. The study was limited to thirty (30) Grade 6 pupils, that is fifteen (15) learners for the experimental group and another fifteen (15) for the control group as respondents. Experimental and control groups were employed to seek answers to the problem. On the other hand, pupils' numerical ability was measured in terms of their scores in pretest and posttest. To achieve the objectives of the study, the experimental research design was employed. A survey questionnaire and the results of pretest and posttest were constructed, validated, and used in acquiring data. The data were tallied, analyzed, and interpreted using appropriate statistical tools such as weighted mean, frequency, and t-test. The results of the study revealed that the majority of the Grade 6 pupils were 10 to 12 years old of age, female, and most of their parents were high school graduates. On the other hand, the numerical ability of the Grade 6 learners in both the control group and experimental group before the conduct of the study in the pretest was at the satisfactory level. After the conduct of the study, the numerical ability of the respondents in the experimental group where the audio-visual presentations were used in teaching addition and subtraction of fractions was outstanding. Based on the findings, it is hereby recommended that the Department of Education (DepEd) shall strengthen its programs and activities in the teaching and learning process of mathematics. It is highly recommended to private elementary schools that mathematics teachers must provide seminars, workshops, and in-service training for mathematics subjects. Parents and learners shall have close coordination with the teachers to maximize learning opportunities for the learners.

Keywords: *audio-visual, numerical, ability, mathematics*

Introduction

Education is necessary for everyone. Education is very important; without education, no one can lead a good life. Teaching and learning are important elements in education. The teacher uses different methods and materials to teach their learners for effective learning. With time, different methods and techniques are entered in the field of education and teacher use different kinds of aids to make effective teaching.

Teaching aids arouse the interest of learners and help the teachers to explain the concepts easily. Audio-visual presentations are those instructional aids that are used in the classroom to encourage the teaching-learning process. As Singh (2005) defines audio-visual presentation, "Any device which by sight and sound increase the individuals' experience, beyond that acquired through reading is described as an audio-visual aid".

Visual presentations are resources that contain information learners can see. Picture help learners see mathematical ideas, which aids understanding. Visual mathematics also facilitates higher-level thinking, enables communication, and helps people see the creativity in mathematics. Posters, videos, anchor charts, etc are all great examples.

The use of visual presentations in a math classroom should capture the learners' attention, and get them interested in the concepts that will be taught. The best audio-visual presentations that could be used in math would be manipulative. By using real objects the learners can visually see, and be hands-on with the concept that is being taught. The audio-visual presentations used in a math class should be appropriate for the lesson, and communicate the message that the teacher wants to convey. All learners can benefit from using visual presentations, although struggling learners may require additional, focused support and practice. Visual representations are a powerful way for learners to access mathematical ideas (Zorfass & Han, 2014).

Lestage (2009) pointed out that technology can never replace the human mind, but it can help expand it. It is the duty of the teachers that use audio-visual presentations that are relevant to the lesson and learners' wrong use and selection of the teaching aids will be a waste of time and energy for nothing. Mathew (2013) stated that it is the responsibility of the teacher to use audio-visual presentations to make the teaching-learning process effective. Shamsideen's (2016) teaching and learning activities are interesting when audio-visual presentations are used effectively and efficiently in a classroom-teaching situation. It is a universal fact that children learn best by observing and copying the behaviors of adults. Sunder (2010) stated that learning is more effective when sensory experiences are stimulated.

Therefore, any device which can be used to make the learning experience most concrete and effective, more realistic and dynamic can be considered audio visual material. We learn through our sense organs. Senses are the ways of knowledge. All the sense organs help us in understanding the environment. Most of the knowledge, which we acquire from school comes from through our eyes and ears.

It is well known among educators that the educational experiences involving the learners actively participating in concretes examples

are retained longer has elements of reality by providing concretes. Examples of learning many authors have written on the use of audio-visual presentations in teaching mathematics and other related subjects to enhance teaching for changes in mental and behavioral change.

Mathematics teaching and learning cannot be well accomplished without the use of instructional materials. The reason is not far-fetched advances in which technology has brought audio-visual presentations to the fore front as the most radical tools of globalization and skillful development which have affected the classroom teaching-learning situation positively. Such technological breakthroughs as network non-world projected and non-projected visual auditory audio-visual electronic materials are important landmarks in knowledge transfer with them both teaching and learning became very effective learning aids are instructional materials and devices learning are done in school. Examples of learning aids are designed materials that may be locally made or commercially produces.

They come to inform of well charts illustrated pictures pictorial materials and other two-dimensional objects. These are also audio-visual presentations. These are teaching machines like radio, television, and all sorts of projectors with sound attributes. It is interesting to note that a large percentage of trained teachers and these undergoing professional training courses can teach with some of the learning aids. They do so consciously because they know that the user has a positive effect on learning outcomes as their cognate experience during teaching practices supervision.

They said that learning aids reduce their talk and chalk method. The experiences of pupils will become will or broad by using such media as television and motion pictures. Learners can learn more even though they are still confined to the four walls of the classroom. For instance, in education television, different ideas and concepts can be taught through real-life experience demonstrations, excursions, etc. They allow learners to come in contact with expert teachers through visual media, learners can successfully show interrelationships among the complex whole. They also help retention of factual knowledge pictures more open than tend to remember what they can see, hear, and touch.

In this regard, this study aims to identify whether the use of audio-visual presentations is effective in teaching mathematics in Gani L. Abpi College, Incorporated-Madia Campus, and to gauge the perception of the learners in the use of audio-visual presentations in their learning. Subsequently, it aims to provide a preliminary framework to optimize the use of audio-visual presentations in the teaching mathematics of elementary grade 6 learners in the private school GLACI-Madia Campus.

Research Questions

Generally, this study aims to determine the effects of audio-visual presentations in teaching Mathematics on learners' numerical ability at GLACI- Madia Campus, Madia, Datu Saudi U. Ampatuan, Maguindanao. Specifically, this research study was designed to answer the following questions:

1. What is the profile of the Grade 6 learners as respondents of this study, in terms of:
 - 1.1. age;
 - 1.2. sex; and
 - 1.3. parents' highest educational attainment?
2. What is the numerical ability of the control group in the pretest on the following topics, such as:
 - 2.1. addition of fractions; and
 - 2.2. subtraction of fractions?
3. What is the numerical ability of the experimental group in the pretest on the following topics, such as:
 - 3.1. addition of fractions; and
 - 3.2. subtraction of fractions?
4. What is the numerical ability of the control group in the posttest on the following topics, such as:
 - 4.1. addition of fractions; and
 - 4.2. subtraction of fractions?
5. What is the numerical ability of the experimental group in the posttest on the following topics, such as:
 - 5.1. addition of fractions; and
 - 5.2. subtraction of fractions?
6. Is there a significant difference between the numerical abilities of the respondents in the control group and the experimental group?

Methodology

Research Design

The quasi-experiment research design was adopted for this study specifically, on the use of a randomized pretest-posttest control group in experimental design. Experimental research design is a framework of protocols and procedures created to conduct experimental research with a scientific approach using two sets of variables (Sirisilla, 2023). In this study, both the learners in the experimental and control groups were given a pretest before experimentation and commenced assessing their learning gains after exposing them to audio-visual aided and traditional methods, respectively.

Respondents

The respondents of the study were the thirty (30) selected Grade 6 learners who are officially enrolled in this School Year 2022-2023 at Glaci-Madia Campus. The researcher used the scales below to determine the numerical ability of learners in additions of fractions and subtractions of fractions. As per the result of the pretest and posttest, the respondents were divided into two (2) groups, fifteen (15) respondents for the control group and another fifteen (15) respondents for the experimental group.

The researcher used purposive sampling in selecting the respondents who were the Grade 6 learners enrolled at Gani L. Abpi College, Incorporated Madia Campus, Madia, Datu Saudi Ampatuan, Maguindanao. All thirty (30) Grade 6 learners were selected as respondents and divided into two (2) groups to form the control group and the experimental group.

Instrument

The research instrument used was a modified questionnaire that consists of two parts, namely; Part I: Personal Profile of Respondents, and Part II consists of the Pretest and Posttest Questionnaire which is composed of twenty-five (25) addition of fractions and another twenty-five 25 subtraction of fraction with the total of fifty (50) items. It is designed to determine the numerical ability of the respondents in the control group and experimental group before and after the teaching and learning activities.

Procedure

The subjects in this study were divided into two groups: the experimental group which was taught with audio-visual presentations using television, laptop, wi-fi, and other teaching materials, and the control group which was taught with the traditional method through the use of books, blackboard, and chalk. The researcher sent letters to the Acting Principal of GLACI- Madia Campus to request permission to begin her research study. Since Gani L. Abpi College, Incorporated has its class schedule, the number of enrollees is limited the pupils were divided into two groups. Batch 1 is for Monday through Wednesday, and Batch 2 is for Tuesday through Thursday.

Here are the following steps on how the researcher processed and gathered data. First, filing the needed data on the profile of the respondents. Before the experiment on the first day of the week, the researcher administered a pre-test to 15 control group respondents, and another pre-test for the experimental group for another 15 respondents on the second day. On the other day, the researcher discusses the lesson (addition and subtraction of fractions) using traditional methods (books, chalk, and blackboard), and on the other day, the discussion (addition and subtraction of fractions) is scheduled to use audio-visual presentations (using television and laptop). Following the conclusion of the lessons, the researcher will administer the post-test to learners in both the control and experimental groups on different dates. The researcher will be marked and recorded the scores. The interest test was administered to the learners. The adviser and Subject Teacher will be assisted in distributing the instrument and answer sheet to the learners. They will also supervise the learners and collect the answer sheets at the end of the test.

Data Analysis

The results of the experiment were computed, analyzed, and interpreted using the mean, percentages, and t-test.

Frequency and percentage were used to describe the socio-demographic profile of the respondents in terms of age, sex, and parents' highest educational attainment.

To test the significant differences of two variables or the mean scores of the control group and experimental group, t-test was used using Excel computations.

Results and Discussion

This section presents the analysis and interpretation of data gathered from the respondents.

Profile of Respondents

Tables 1 to 3 present in tabular form the demographic profile of the thirty (30) grade six pupils/learners who were the respondents of this study. This profile is in terms of age, sex, and parents' highest educational attainment.

Age Profile

Table 1 presents the distribution of Grade 6 learners by age in the experimental group and control group. The age of respondents were categorized into two (2) such as; 10 to 12 years old, 13 years old, and above.

Table 1. Age Distribution of the Respondents in the Experimental Group

Age	Grade 6 Learners in the Experimental Group	
	Frequency (f)	Percentage (%)
10-12	10	67
13 and above	5	33
Total	15	100

As indicated in Table 1, (67%) of the respondents in the experimental group have aged ranging from 10 to 12 years old while thirty-three (33%) were 13 years old and above. This means that the majority of the Grade 6 learners were in the aged range of 10 to 12 years old.

Table 2. Age Distribution of the Respondents in the Control Group

Age	Grade 6 Learners in Control Group	
	Frequency (f)	Percentage (%)
10-12	11	73
13 and above	4	27
Total	15	100

As indicated in Table 2, seventy-three (73%) of the learners in the control group have aged ranging from 10 to 12 years old got while twenty-seven (27%) or five respondents were in the aged range of 13 years old and above. This means that in the control group, most of the respondents are aged 10 to 12 years old.

Sex Profile

Tables 3 and 4 present the distribution of Grade 6 learners by sex in the experimental group and control group, that is, male or female.

Table 3 presents the sex distribution of the Grade 6 learners in the experimental group.

Table 3. Sex Distribution of the Respondents in the Experimental Group

Sex	Grade 6 Learners in the Experimental Group	
	Frequency (f)	Percentage (%)
Male	5	33
Female	10	67
Total	15	100

The data in Table 3 above shows the sex classification of the Grade 6 learners in the experimental group who were the respondents of this study. As shown, thirty-three (33%) of the learners were males while sixty-seven (67%) were females. This means that there are more females than males in Grade 6 learners at GLACI - Madia Campus.

Table 4. Sex Distribution of the Respondents in the Control Group

Sex	Grade 6 Learners in Control Group	
	Frequency (f)	Percentage (%)
Male	4	27
Female	11	73
Total	15	100

The data in Table 4 shows the sex classification of the Grade 6 learners who were the respondents of this study in the control group. As shown, twenty-seven (27%) of the respondents were males while seventy-three (73%) were females. This implies that the majority of the respondents in graduating class were females for both experimental and control groups.

Parents' Highest Educational Attainment

Tables 5 and 6 present the distribution of the Grade 6 learners according to parents' highest educational attainment in the experimental group and control group.

Table 5. Distribution of the Grade 6 Learners in the Experimental Group According to their Parents' Highest Educational Attainment

Parents' Highest Educational Attainment	Grade 6 Learners in the Experimental Group	
	Frequency (f)	Percentage (%)
Elementary Graduate	1	7
High School Graduate	10	66
College Undergraduate	1	7
College Graduate	3	20
Total	15	100

Table 5 presents the parents' highest educational attainment of the Grade 6 learners in the experimental group. As shown, the majority, or 66% of the parents of the respondents were high school graduates while twenty percent of them were college graduates.

As shown in Table 6, the majority of the parents of the Grade 6 learners in the control group had parents whose highest educational attainment is high school graduate as indicated by the sixty-six percent (66%) percentage. On the other hand, twenty-seven percent (27%) were elementary graduates and only seven percent (7%) were college graduates.

Table 6. *Distribution of the Grade 6 Learners in the Control Group According to their Parents' Highest Educational Attainment*

Parents' Highest Educational Attainment	Grade 6 Learners in Control Group	
	Frequency (f)	Percentage (%)
Elementary Graduate	4	27
High School Graduate	10	66
College Undergraduate	1	7
College Graduate	0	0
Total	15	100

The results implied that in both the experimental group and control group their parents had gone to school but most of them reached only a high school level of education.

The Numerical Ability of the Respondents in the Pretest

The numerical ability of the Grade 6 learners before the conduct of the study in the control group and experimental group.

Table 7. *Respondents' Numerical Ability in the Pretest in the Control Group*

Topic	Male	Female	Mean	Interpretation
Addition of Fractions	10.75	11.82	11.29	Satisfactory
Subtraction of Fractions	10.00	9.36	9.68	Fairly Satisfactory
Mean	10.38	10.59	10.49	Satisfactory

Legend: 20.00–25.00 Outstanding (O), 15.00–19.99 Very Satisfactory (VS), 10.00–14.99 Satisfactory (S), 5.00–9.99 Fairly Satisfactory (FS), 0.00–4.99 Did Not Meet the Expectation

As shown in Table 7, the numerical ability of the Grade 6 learners in the control group before the conduct of the study is “satisfactory” as revealed by the mean of 10.49. As observed, the learners' performance in the addition of fractions has a mean of 11.29, which fall under the “satisfactory” level while in the subtraction of fractions; the mean of their performance is 9.68, which falls under the “fairly satisfactory” level. This means that the learners were more familiar with the addition of fractions than the subtraction of fractions.

Consequently, the female learners have a higher mean score of 11.82 compared to the males with 10.75 in the addition of fractions while the male pupils have a higher mean score of 10.00 compared to the females' mean score of 9.36 in subtraction of fractions. It implies that female respondents were more familiar with the addition of fractions than the subtraction of fractions while their male counterparts were more familiar with the subtraction of fractions.

Table 8. *Respondents' Numerical Ability in the Pretest in the Experimental Group*

Topic	Male	Female	Mean	Interpretation
Addition of Fractions	11.80	12.30	12.05	Satisfactory
Subtraction of Fractions	10.20	10.00	10.01	Satisfactory
Mean	11	11.2	11.03	Satisfactory

Legend: 20.00–25.00 Outstanding (O), 15.00–19.99 Very Satisfactory (VS), 10.00–14.99 Satisfactory (S), 5.00–9.99 Fairly Satisfactory (FS), 0.00–4.99 Did Not Meet the Expectation

As shown in Table 8, the numerical ability of the Grade 6 learners under the experimental group before the intervention made or pretest. It shows that a grand mean of 11.03 indicates that the level of performance of the learners was satisfactory. The addition of fractions is seen to be the highest score gained by the respondents in addition of fractions with a mean of 12.30 were females and an interpretation of satisfactory while in subtraction of fractions males got the highest mean score of 10.20 as revealed of satisfactory. This means female respondents were familiar with the addition of fractions while male respondents were more familiar with subtractions of fractions.

The Numerical Ability of the Respondents in the Posttest

The numerical ability of the Grade 6 learners after the conduct of the study in the control group and experimental group.

Table 9. *Respondents' Numerical Ability in the Posttest in the Control Group*

Topic	Male	Female	Mean	Interpretation
Addition of Fractions	16.00	17.36	16.7	Very Satisfactory
Subtraction of Fractions	15.75	16.36	16.1	Very Satisfactory
Mean	15.9	16.9	16.4	Very Satisfactory

Legend: 20.00–25.00 Outstanding (O), 15.00–19.99 Very Satisfactory (VS), 10.00–14.99 Satisfactory (S), 5.00–9.99 Fairly Satisfactory (FS), 0.00–4.99 Did Not Meet the Expectation

As shown in Table 9, the numerical ability of the Grade 6 learners in the control group after the study is “very satisfactory” as revealed by the mean of 16.4. As observed, the pupils' performance in the addition of fractions has a mean of 16.7, which fall under the “very satisfactory” level while in the subtraction of fractions, the mean of their performance is 16.1, which falls under the “very satisfactory”

level. This means that the learners were more familiar with the addition of fractions than the subtraction of fractions.

Therefore, the female learners have a higher mean score of 17.36 compared to the males with 16.00 in the addition of fractions while the male learners have a lower mean score of 15.75 compared to the females' mean score of 16.9 in subtraction of fractions. It demonstrates that female learners learned more quickly than male pupils.

Table 10 presents the numerical ability of the Grade 6 learners in the experimental group in the posttest.

Table 10. Respondents' Numerical Ability in the Posttest in the Experimental Group

Topic	Male	Female	Mean	Interpretation
Addition of Fractions	21.60	22.70	22.2	Outstanding
Subtraction of Fractions	21.00	22.00	21.5	Outstanding
Mean	21.3	22.4	21.9	Outstanding

Legend: 20.00–25.00 Outstanding (O), 15.00–19.99 Very Satisfactory (VS), 10.00–14.99 Satisfactory (S), 5.00–9.99 Fairly Satisfactory (FS), 0.00–4.99 Did Not Meet the Expectation

As shown in Table 10, the numerical ability of the Grade 6 learners in the experimental group after the study was "Outstanding," as revealed by the mean of 21.9. According to the results, the pupils' performance in the addition of fractions has a mean of 22.2, which falls under the "Outstanding" level, whereas their performance in the subtraction of fractions has a mean of 21.5, which falls under the "Outstanding" level. This indicates that the learners were more familiar with fraction addition than fraction subtraction.

As a result, female pupils have a higher mean score of 22.70 compared to males with 21.60 in addition of fractions, while male pupils have a mean score of 21.00 compared to females' mean score of 22.00 in subtraction of fractions. This shows that female pupils were more likely to learn than male pupils.

Differences between the Numerical Abilities of the Grade 6 Pupils in the Control Group and Experimental Group in the Pretest and Posttest

The following tables present the differences in the performances of the Grade 6 pupils in the control group and experimental group in the following topics such as the addition of fractions and subtraction of fractions.

Differences in Grade 6 Pupils' Numerical Abilities on Addition of Fractions

Table 11 presents the differences in the Grade 6 pupils' numerical abilities on the addition of fractions in the control group and experimental group in the posttest.

Table 11. T-Test Analysis on the Grade 6 Learners' Numerical Abilities on Addition of Fractions in the Control Group and Experimental Group

Group	MPS	t-comp	t-ratio	Interpretation
Control Group	17	2.45	1.75	* Significant
Experimental Group	22.333			

* Significant @ .05 level of confidence

As can be seen in Table 8, the computed t-ratio, 1.75 is lower than the critical value of 2.45 at a .05 level of significance. The t-ratio reveals the rejection of the null hypothesis that there is no significant difference between the numerical abilities of the learners in the control group and the experimental group. This means that there is a significant difference between the performance of the learners exposed to audio-visual materials and the chalk and board method. The pupils who were taught fractions using the audio-visual materials performed better than those pupils taught using the chalk and board method.

In a study conducted by Biyani (2013), no difference in performance was found between younger teachers and older teachers. Though the older teachers have more teaching experiences than the younger ones, their performance in the school in teaching the learners is the same. Hassan (2013) also revealed the same findings. According to him, there is no significant difference between the teachers' performance when they are classified according to their ages. Teachers also explained that the use of audio-visual presentations saves energy and time which supports the findings of Aina (2006) that the use of teaching aids in the teaching-learning process also saves time and helps teachers in completing their syllabus timely. They also recommended that teaching aids make the teaching-learning process effective and result oriented which supports Rasul's (2011) audio-visual presentations make the teaching-learning process effective and motivate teachers and learners.

Table 12 presents the differences in the Grade 6 learners' numerical abilities in subtraction of fractions in the control group and experimental group after the teaching and learning activities.

As shown in the table are the Grade 6 learners' numerical abilities in subtraction of fractions in the control group (16.2) and experimental group (21.666). The t-test Analysis shows that the computed t-ratio of 1.75 is significant the t-computed value of 2.8 is greater at a .05 level of confidence. The t-ratio reveals the rejection of the null hypothesis that there is no significant difference between the numerical abilities of the learners in the control group and the experimental group. This means that there is a significant difference between the

performance of the learners exposed to audio-visual presentations and the chalk-and-board method. Based on these findings, it is acceptable and appropriate to say that the use of audio-visual presentations in subtractions of fractions is more effective than the use of the traditional method chalk and blackboard.

Table 12. *T-Test Analysis on the Grade 6 Pupils' Numerical Abilities on Subtraction of Fractions in the Control Group and Experimental Group*

Group	MPS	t-comp	t-ratio	Interpretation
Control Group	16.2	2.18	1.75	* Significant
Experimental Group	21.666			

* Significant @ .05 level of confidence

As shown in the table are the Grade 6 learners' numerical abilities in subtraction of fractions in the control group (16.2) and experimental group (21.666). The t-test Analysis shows that the computed t-ratio of 1.75 is significant the t-computed value of 2.8 is greater at a .05 level of confidence. The t-ratio reveals the rejection of the null hypothesis that there is no significant difference between the numerical abilities of the learners in the control group and the experimental group. This means that there is a significant difference between the performance of the learners exposed to audio-visual presentations and the chalk-and-board method. Based on these findings, it is acceptable and appropriate to say that the use of audio-visual presentations in subtractions of fractions is more effective than the use of the traditional method chalk and blackboard.

Audio-visual presentations support the findings of Ode (2014) that there is a significant difference between learners who are taught with or without the use of audio-visual presentations. It also supports the findings of Parul (2012) that audio-visual presentations have a significant effect on the achievement of learners. Billaiya (2017) also found that learning through audio-visual presentations was higher. Aggarwal (2012) also found that learners of the study group with audio-visual aids outperformed those of the control group with no availability of these aids.

Conclusions

Based on the summary of findings presented above, the following conclusions were drawn:

The academic performance of Grade 6 learners who were taught using audio-visual presentations was superior to the learners who were taught using a traditional method because using audio-visual presentations when teaching mathematics helps learners remember the concept, particularly the addition, and subtraction of fractions, for a longer period.

Moreover, there are several problems in implementing audio-visual presentations because not all classroom has their own audio-visual that should be used in teaching, with that school administrators and BARMM Officials should give necessary actions.

Based on the finding of this study, the researcher recommends that;

The teachers must always use audio-visual presentations as part of their motivation, presentation, discussion, and evaluation of the lesson to make meaningful learning for the pupils.

Stakeholders in the educational sectors like administrators and parents should help to provide some of the audio-visual presentations in the school.

School Administrators must provide seminars, workshops, conferences, and in-service training programs for mathematics subject teachers to update their skills as well as how to improvise some of these teaching aids.

MBHTE-BARMM must provide financial assistance to the school to provide some useful audio-visual materials.

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